

Analysis of wireless data transfer methods for subcutaneous medical implants

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Abstract: Inductive and ultrasonic data transfer methods for subcutaneous medical implants are compared based on parameters such as power consumption, component size, data security, harmfulness to the body, data rate and susceptibility to failure. Advantages and disadvantages are described, making both methods suitable for different applications.

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I. Introduction

Smart implants are playing an increasingly important role in medicine as seen for example in personalized treatment of bone fractures by monitoring callus formation using sensors and accelerating bone healing through stimulation [1]. This requires the ability to transmit data wirelessly. Methods for this include, for example, inductive and ultrasonic data transfer [2]. This paper reviews and analyzes these two popular wireless data transfer methods for subcutaneous medical implants.

II. Methods

A literature review of recent developments of inductive and ultrasonic data transfer is conducted. The parameters defined for the comparison of the two methods are shown in Table 1. These result from the requirements for data transfer systems for subcutaneous medical implants, such as security, fast and energy-saving data transfer, the use of small components and a high level of safety for the patient.

III. Results

The comparison of inductive and ultrasonic data transfer regarding the various parameters is shown in Table 1. The details of the individual parameters are described below.

III.I. Power consumption

A range of different systems is considered when analyzing power consumption, which leads to high standard deviations. The mean value of the power consumption with simultaneous data and power transmission is calculated using the data from [3]. Outliers¹ are not included.

With inductive systems, the mean value is 4.63 mW with a population of 14 and a standard deviation of 3.96 mW. One outlier, with the value 23.9 mW [4] was defined. For ultrasonic systems, the mean value is 0.86 mW with a

population of 5 and a standard deviation of 0.97 mW. The value 3.2 mW [5] is regarded as an outlier.

III.II. Component size

The size of the coil cannot be reduced arbitrarily, as the size affects its properties. However, other components of the circuit can be assembled compactly [6]. Consequently, the coil is the limiting factor for the size of inductive systems. In [6] a coil with a diameter of 20 mm is presented. The main element of ultrasonic systems, the ultrasonic transducer, can be just a few millimeters in size [7]. An implant for ultrasonic power and data transfer measuring 6.5 mm x 2.6 mm x 1.8 mm is presented in [8].

III.III. Data security

Since inductive communication takes place in the near-field [3], intercepting is difficult. An ordinary antenna must be placed at a distance of approximately 20 cm from the system in order to listen to the communication [9]. Simple intercepting with ultrasonic communication is not possible without physical contact [10].

III.IV. Harmfulness to the body

The tissue surrounding the implant can heat up due to the absorbed electromagnetic waves. This can be avoided by limiting field intensity and frequency of the system [2]. The absorption of the ultrasonic waves by the tissue also leads to heating. The transmission power is therefore limited by the maximum compatible tissue temperature [7].

Barium, lead and bismuth, which are contained in various piezoceramics, are toxic. It is therefore necessary to encapsulate these piezoceramics when they are implanted in the body to use ultrasonic communication [7].

III.V. Data rate

As with the analysis of power consumption, a wide range of systems is considered. The data from [3] is used to

¹ An outlier is defined as a value that is higher than the sum of the mean value and 1.5 times the standard deviation.

calculate the mean value of the data rate without considering outliers.

The mean value of the data rate for inductive uplink communication is 778.51 kbps with a population of 15 and a standard deviation of 1339.36 kbps. The value of 8000 kbps [11] is defined as an outlier. For the uplink of ultrasonic systems, the mean value is 35.12 kbps with a population of 7 and a standard deviation of 37.20 kbps. An outlier with the value 784 kbps [12] is disregarded.

The mean value of the data rate for inductive downlink communication is 637.24 kbps with a population of 24 and a standard deviation of 718.10 kbps. The outliers are 4000 kbps [13, 14], 4160 kbps [15] and 8000 kbps [11]. For ultrasonic downlink communication, the mean value of the data rate is 460.75 kbps with a population of 12 and a standard deviation of 1369.56 kbps. The values of 20000 kbps [16] and 30000 kbps [16] are defined as outliers.

III.VI. Susceptance to failure

Electromagnetic interference (EMI) can occur in inductive systems, either by components in the system or by external sources [2]. In ultrasonic systems, sound waves can be reflected or scattered due to different acoustic properties of various structures. This multipath effect has an impact on the propagation of the ultrasound, but is not as relevant for data transmission through shallow tissue [7]. Additionally, simple jamming of ultrasonic communication is not possible without physical contact [10].

IV. Discussion and conclusions

In this paper, the methods of inductive and ultrasonic data transfer were analyzed and compared with each other based on various parameters. The advantages of inductive data transfer over ultrasonic data transfer are the higher data rate and the smaller harmfulness to the body. The latter can be explained by the toxicity of piezoceramics in ultrasonic systems [7]. Ultrasonic data transfer has the advantages of lower power consumption and a smaller component size as well as higher data security. The higher data security results from the fact that a physical contact is necessary [10], whereas with an inductive system, proximity alone is sufficient for intercepting [9]. Susceptance to failure is similar for both data transfer methods. However, the type of disturbance that can occur with the two data transfer methods is different.

Table 1: Comparison of inductive and ultrasonic data transfer

Parameter	Inductive data transfer	Ultrasonic data transfer
Power consumption	Higher	Lower
Component size	Higher	Lower
Data security	Lower	Higher
Harmfulness to the body	Lower	Higher
Data rate	Higher	Lower
Susceptance to failure	Similar	

As shown in this paper, both methods of data transfer have different advantages and disadvantages, which is why the appropriate method must be selected for each implantable medical system, depending on the application.

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